

PROPERTIES OF γ - PARACOMPACT SPACES

P. Senthil Kumar* & S. Sangeetha**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Raja Serfoji Government College,
 Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, Raja Serfoji Government College,
 Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

A kind of new paracompactness axiom is introduced in L-topological spaces, where L is a fuzzy lattice. And its topological properties are systematically studied.

1. Introduction:

It is known that paracompactness and its stronger and weaker forms play very important roles in topology. Based on fuzzy topological spaces introduced by Chang [1], various kinds of fuzzy compactness [1, 4, 10] have been established. However, these concepts of fuzzy compactness rely on the structure of L and L is required to be completely distributive. In [9], for a complete De Morgan algebra L, Shi introduced a new definition of fuzzy compactness in L – topological spaces using open L – sets and their inequality. This new definition does not depend on the structure of L. In this paper, A kind of new paracompactness axiom is introduced in L – topological spaces, where L is a fuzzy lattice. And its topological properties are systematically studied.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper X and Y will be nonempty ordinary sets and $L = L(<, \vee, \wedge ')$ will denote a fuzzy lattice, that is, a completely distributive lattice with a smallest element 0 and largest element 1 ($0 \neq 1$) and with an order reversion involution $a \rightarrow a'$ ($a \in L$). We shall denote by L^X the lattice of all L – subsets of X and if $A \in X$ by X_A the characteristic function of A. An L-topological space is a pair (X, τ) , where τ is a sub family of L^X which contains $\underline{0}, \underline{1}$ and is closed for any suprema and finite infima. τ is called an open L – set and its quasi complementation is called a closed L – set. An element p of L is called prime if, and only if $p \neq 1$ and whenever $a, b \in L$ with $a \wedge b \leq p$ then $a \leq p$ or $b \leq p$ [3, 4]. The set of all prime elements of L will be denoted by $pr(L)$. An element α of L is called union irreducible or coprime if, and only if whenever $a, b \in L$ with $\alpha \leq a \vee b$ then $\alpha \leq a$ or $\alpha \leq b$ [3]. The set of all non zero union irreducible elements of L will be denoted by $M(L)$. It is obvious that $p \in pr(L)$ if, and only if $p' \in M(L)$. Warner [12] has determined the prime element of the fuzzy lattice L^X . We have $pr(L^X) = \{x_p : x \in X \text{ and } p \in pr(L)\}$, where for each $x \in X$ and each $p \in pr(L)$, $x_p : X \rightarrow L$ is the L – subset defined by

$$x_p(y) = \begin{cases} p & \text{if } y=x, \\ 1 & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

These x_p are called the L-points of X and we say that x_p is a member of an L-subset f and write $x_p \in f$ if, and only if $f(x) \leq p$. Thus, the union irreducible elements of L^X are the function $x_\alpha : X \rightarrow L$ defined by,

$$x_\alpha(y) = \begin{cases} \alpha & \text{if } y=x, \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $x \in X$ and $\alpha \in M(L)$. Hence, we have $M(L^X) = \{x_\alpha : x \in X \text{ and } \alpha \in M(L)\}$. As these x_α are identified with the L-points x_p of X, we shall refer to them as fuzzy points. When $x_\alpha \in M(L^X)$, we call x and α the support of x_α ($x = \text{Supp } x_\alpha$) and the height of x_α ($\alpha = h(x_\alpha)$), respectively.

Definition 2.1 [5]: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $A \in L^X$. Then A is called a γ -open set if $A \leq \text{Int}(\text{Cl}A) \vee \text{Cl}(\text{Int}A)$. The complement of a γ -open set is called a γ -closed set. Also, $\gamma O(L^X)$ and $\gamma C(L^X)$ will always denote the family of all γ -open sets and γ -closed sets respectively. Obviously, $A \in \gamma O(L^X)$ if, and only if $A' \in \gamma O(L^X)$.

Definition 2.2 [5]: Let (L^X, τ) be an L-topological space, $A, B \in L^X$. Let $\gamma \text{Int}(A) = \vee \{B \in L^X \setminus B \leq A, B \in \gamma O(L^X)\}$, $\gamma \text{Cl}(A) = \wedge \{B \in L^X \setminus A \leq B, B \in \gamma C(L^X)\}$. Then $\gamma \text{Int}(A)$ and $\gamma \text{Cl}(A)$ are called the γ -interior and γ -closure of A respectively.

Definition 2.3 [5]: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L-topological spaces. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called γ -continuous if, and only if $f^{-1}(g)$ is γ -open in (X, τ) , for each $g \in \sigma$.

Definition 2.4: Let $\alpha \in M(L)$ and $g \in L^X$, A collection η of L-subsets is said to form an α -level filter base in the L-subset g if, and only if for any finite subcollection $\{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ of η , there exists $x \in X$. with $g(x) \geq \alpha$ such that

$(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n f_i)(x) \geq \alpha$. When g is the whole space X , then η is an α -level filter base if, and only if for any finite subcollection $\{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ of η , there exists $x \in X$ such that $(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n f_i)(x) \geq \alpha$.

Lemma 2.5 [9]: Let (X, τ) be a topological space, f be an L -subset in the L -ts $(X, \omega(\tau))$ and $p \in \text{pr}(L)$. Then we have

1. $(\text{Cl}(f))^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\}) \subset (\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})))$
2. $(\text{Int}(f))^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\}) \subset (\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})))$

Lemma 2.6 [9]: Let (X, τ) be a topological space and $A \subset X$. Considering the L -ts $(X, \omega(\tau))$ and

$$f(X) = \begin{cases} e \in L & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

We have the following

$$\text{Cl}(f)(X) = \begin{cases} e & \text{if } x \in \text{Cl}(A), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\text{Int}(f)(X) = \begin{cases} e & \text{if } x \in \text{Int}(A), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.7 [6]: Let (X, τ) be an L -ts and $g \in L^X, r \in L$.

1. A collection $\mu = \{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ of L -subsets is called an r -level cover of g if, and only if $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \leq r$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq r$. If each f_i is open then μ is called an r -level open cover of g . If g is the whole space X , then μ is called an r -level cover of X if, and only if $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \leq r$ for all $x \in X$.
2. An r -level cover $\mu = \{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ of g is said to have a finite r -level subcover if there exists a finite subset F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i)(x) \leq r$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq r$.

Definition 2.8: Let (X, τ) be an L -ts and $g \in L^X$. Then g is said to be compact [7] if, and only if for every prime $p \in L$ and every collection $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ of open L -subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p$, there exists

a finite subset F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i)(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p$, that is, every p -level open cover of g

has a finite p -level subcover, where $p \in \text{pr}(L)$. If g is the whole space, then the L -ts (X, τ) is called compact.

3. γ -Compactness and Its Goodness:

Definition 3.1: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space and $g \in L^X$. The g is called γ -compact if, and only if every p -level cover of g consisting of γ -open L -subsets has a finite p -level subcover, where $p \in \text{pr}(L)$. If g is the whole space, then we say that the L -topological space (X, τ) is γ -compact.

Lemma 3.2: Let (X, τ) be a topological space and $A \subset X$. If A is γ -open in (X, τ) , then χ_A is γ -open in the L -topological space $(X, \omega(t))$.

Proof: The proof is clear.

Theorem 3.3: Let (X, τ) be a topological space. Then (X, τ) is γ -compact if, and only if the L -topological space $(X, \omega(t))$ is γ -compact.

Proof: Let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a p -level γ -open cover of $(X, \omega(t))$. Then $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$. Hence

for each $x \in X$ there is $i \in J$ such that $f_i(x) \leq p$, that is, $x \in f_i^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})$. So, $X = \bigcup_{i \in J} f_i^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})$.

Because f_i is γ -open in $(X, \omega(t))$, $f_i^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})$ is γ -open in (X, τ) . Thus $\{f_i^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})\}_{i \in J}$ is a γ -open cover of (X, τ) . Since (X, τ) is γ -compact, there is a finite subset F of J such that $X = \bigcup_{i \in F} f_i^{-1}(\{t \in L: t \leq p\})$, that is

$(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i)(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$. Hence $(X, \omega(t))$ is γ -compact. Conversely let $\{A_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a γ -open cover of (X, τ) . Then

by Lemma 3.2 $\{X_{A_i}\}_{i \in J}$ is a family of γ -open L -subsets in $(X, \omega(t_1), \omega(t_2))$ such that $1 = (\bigvee_{i \in J} X_{A_i})(x) \leq p$ for all

$x \in X$ and for all $p \in \text{pr}(L)$, that is $\{X_{A_i}\}_{i \in J}$ is a p -level γ -open cover of $(X, \omega(t))$. Since $(X, \omega(t))$ is γ -compact,

there is a finite F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in J} X_{A_i})(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$. Hence $(\bigvee_{i \in F} X_{A_i})(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$, that is,

$$X = \bigcup_{i \in F} A_i \text{ and therefore, } (X, \tau) \text{--compact.}$$

Theorem 3.4: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. Then $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact if, and only if for every $\alpha \in M(L)$ and every collection $\{h_i\}_{i \in J}$ of γ -closed L -subsets with $(\bigwedge_{i \in J} h_i)(x) \geq \alpha$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$, there is a finite subset F of J such that $(\bigwedge_{i \in F} h_i)(x) \geq \alpha$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$.

Proof: This follows immediately from Definition 3.1

Theorem 3.5 Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. Then $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact if, and only if for every $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and every collection $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ of γ -open L -subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i v g')(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$, there is a finite subset F of

$$J \text{ such that } (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Proof: Let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collection of γ -open L -subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i v g')(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$. Then

$$(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X \text{ with } g(x) \geq p'. \text{ Since } g \text{ is } \gamma\text{-compact, there is a finite subset } F \text{ of } J \text{ such that}$$

$$(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X \text{ with } g(x) \geq p'. \text{ Take an arbitrary } x \in X. \text{ If } g'(x) \leq p, \text{ then } g'(x) v (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x))$$

$$= (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ because } (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x)) \leq p. \text{ If } g'(x) \leq p, \text{ then we have } g'(x) v (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x)) = (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p. \text{ Thus,}$$

$$\text{we have } (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X. \text{ Conversely, let } p \in \text{pr}(L) \text{ and } \{f_i\}_{i \in J} \text{ be a collection of a } p\text{-level, } \gamma\text{-}$$

$$\text{open cover of } g. \text{ Then } (\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X. \text{ with } g(x) \geq p'. \text{ Hence } (\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X. \text{ From}$$

$$\text{the hypothesis, there is a finite subset } F \text{ of } J \text{ such that } (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for all } x \in X. \text{ Then } (\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i v g')(x) \leq p \text{ for}$$

all $x \in X$ with $g'(x) \leq p'$. Thus g is γ -compact.

Definition 3.6: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. X_α be an L -point in $M(L^X)$ and $S = (S_m)_{m \in D}$ be a net, X_α is called γ -cluster point of S if, and only if for each γ -closed L -subset f with $f(x) \geq \alpha$ and for all $n \in D$, there is $m \in D$ such that $m \geq n$ and $S_m \leq f$, that is, $h(S_m) \leq f(\text{Supp } S_m)$.

Theorem 3.7: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. Then $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact if, and only if every constant α net in g , where $\alpha \in M(L)$, has a γ -cluster point in g with height α .

Proof: Let $\alpha \in M(L)$ and $S = (S_m)_{m \in D}$ be a constant α -net in g without any γ -cluster point with height α in g . Then for each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$, X_α is not a γ -cluster point of S , that is, there are $n_x \in D$ and a γ -closed, L -subset f_x with $f_x(x) \geq \alpha$ and $S_m \leq f_x$ for each $m \geq n_x$. Let $x_1, \dots, x_k$ be elements of X with $g(x_i) \geq \alpha$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. Then there are $n_{x_1}, \dots, n_{x_k} \in D$ and γ -closed L -subset f_{x_i} with $f_{x_i}(x_i) \geq \alpha$ and $S_m \leq f_{x_i}$ for each $m \geq n_{x_i}$ and for each $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. Since D is a directed set, there is $n_0 \in D$ such that $n_0 \geq n_{x_i}$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ and $S_m \leq f_{x_i}$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ and each $m \geq n_0$. Now, consider the family $\mu = \{f_x\}_{x \in X}$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$. Then $(\bigwedge_{f_x \in \mu} f_x)(y) \geq \alpha$ for all

$$y \in X \text{ with } g(y) \geq \alpha \text{ because } f_y(y) \geq \alpha. \text{ We also have that for any finite subfamily } \nu = \{f_{x_1}, \dots, f_{x_k}\} \text{ of } \mu, \text{ there is}$$

$$y \in X \text{ with } g(y) \geq \alpha \text{ and } (\bigwedge_{i=1}^k f_{x_i})(y) \geq \alpha \text{ since } S_m \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^k f_{x_i} \text{ for } m \geq n_0 \text{ because } S_m \leq f_{x_i} \text{ for each } m \geq n_0.$$

Hence, by Theorem 3.5, g is not γ -compact. Conversely, suppose that g is not γ -compact. Then by

Theorem 3.5, there exist $\alpha \in M(L)$ and a collection $\mu = \{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ of γ -closed L -subsets with $(\bigwedge_{i \in J} f_i)(x) \geq \alpha$ for all

$$x \in X \text{ with } g(x) \geq \alpha, \text{ but for any finite subfamily } \nu \text{ of } \mu \text{ there is } x \in X \text{ with } g(x) \geq \alpha \text{ and } (\bigwedge_{i \in J} f_i)(x) < \alpha$$

. Consider the family of all finite subsets of μ , $2^{(\mu)}$, with the order $\nu_1 \leq \nu_2$ if, and only if $\nu_1 \subset \nu_2$. Then $2^{(\mu)}$ is a

directed set. So, writing x_α as S_ν for every $\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}$, $(X_\nu)_{\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}}$ is a constant α -net in g because the height of S_ν for all $\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}$ is α and $S_\nu \leq g$ for all $\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}$, that is $g(x) \not\geq \alpha$. $(S_\nu)_{\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}}$ also satisfies the condition that for each

γ -closed L-subset, $f_i \in \nu$ we have $x_\alpha = S_\nu \leq f_i$. Let $y \in X$ with $g(y) \geq \alpha$. Then $(\bigwedge_{i \in J} f_i)(y) \geq \alpha$, that is, there exists

$j \in J$ with $f_j(y) \geq \alpha$. Let $\nu_0 = \{f_j\}$. So, for any $\nu \geq \nu_0$, $S_\nu \leq \bigwedge_{f_i \in \nu} f_i \leq \bigwedge_{f_i \in \nu_0} f_i = f_j$. Thus, we get a γ -closed L-subset. f_j

with $f_j(y) \geq \alpha$ and $\nu_0 \in 2^{(\mu)}$ such that for any $\nu \geq \nu_0$, $S_\nu \leq f_j$. That means that $y_\alpha \in M(L^X)$ is not a γ -cluster point $(X_\nu)_{\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}}$ for all $y \in X$ with $g(y) \geq \alpha$. Hence, the constant α -net $(S_\nu)_{\nu \in 2^{(\mu)}}$ has no γ -cluster point in g with height α .

Corollary 3.8: An L-topological space is (X, τ) γ -compact if, and only if every constant α -net in (X, τ) has a γ -cluster point with height α , where $\alpha \in M(L)$

Definition 3.9: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and η an α -level filter base, where $\alpha \in M(L)$. An L-point

$x_r \in M(L^X)$ is called a γ -cluster point of η , if $\bigwedge_{f \in \eta} \gamma Cl(f)(x) \geq r$.

Theorem 3.10: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. Then $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact if, and only if every α -filter base in g , where $\alpha \in M(L)$, α - γ -cluster point x_α in g with height α .

Proof: Assume that η is an α -level filter base in g with no γ -cluster point in g with height α , where $\alpha \in M(L)$. Then for each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$, x_α is not a γ -cluster point of η , that is, there is $f_x \in \eta$ with $\gamma Cl(f_x)(x) \not\geq \alpha$. Hence $\gamma Cl(f_x)'(x) \not\geq \alpha = p \in \text{pr}(L)$. This means that the collection $\{\gamma Cl(f_x)'\}_{x \in X}$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$ is a p -level γ -open

cover of g . Since g is γ -compact, there $\gamma Cl(f_{x_1}), \dots, \gamma Cl(f_{x_n})$ such that $\bigvee_{i=1}^n \gamma Cl(f_{x_i})'(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with

$g(x) \geq \alpha$. Hence $\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \gamma Cl(f_{x_i})'(x) \not\geq \alpha$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq \alpha$ which implies that $(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n f_{x_i})(x) \not\geq \alpha$ for all $x \in X$

with $g(x) \geq \alpha$. This is a contradiction. Conversely, suppose that g is not γ -compact. Then there is a p -level γ -open cover μ of g with no finite p -level subcover, where $p \in \text{pr}(L)$. Hence for each finite sub collection

$\{h_1, \dots, h_n\}$ of μ , there exists $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$ such that $(\bigvee_{i=1}^n (h_i(x) \leq p)$, that is, $(\bigvee_{i=1}^n (h_i(x) \geq p') = \alpha \in M(L)$. Thus

$\eta = \{h : h \in \mu\}$ forms an α -level filter base in g . By the hypothesis, μ has a γ -cluster point $y_\alpha \in M(L^X)$ in g with

height α , that is, $g(y) \geq \alpha$ and $\bigwedge_{h \in \mu} \gamma Cl(h')(y) = \bigwedge_{h \in \mu} h'(y) \geq \alpha$. Then $\bigwedge_{h \in \mu} h'(y) \leq p$, which yields a contradiction.

Corollary 3.11: An L-topological space (X, τ) is γ -compact if, and only if every α -filter base has α - γ -cluster point with height α , where $\alpha \in M(L)$.

Theorem 3.12: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $g, h \in L^X$. If g and h are γ -compact then $g \vee h$ is γ -compact.

Proof: Let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collections of γ -open L-subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with

$(g \vee h)(x) \geq p'$. Since p is prime, we have $(g \vee h)(x) \geq p'$ if, and only if $g(x) \geq p'$ or $h(x) \geq p'$. So, by the γ -compactness of g and h , there are finite subsets E, F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in E} f_i(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$ and $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x) \leq p$

for all $x \in X$ with $h(x) \geq p'$. Then $(\bigvee_{i \in E \cup F} f_i(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with $h(x) \geq p'$ or $h(x) \geq p'$, that is, $(\bigvee_{i \in E \cup F} f_i(x) \leq p$ for

all $x \in X$ with $h(x) \geq p'$ or $h(x) \geq p'$. Thus $g \vee h$ is γ -compact.

Theorem 3.13: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $g, h \in L^X$. If f is γ -compact and h is γ -closed, then $g \wedge h$ is γ -compact.

Proof: Let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collections of γ -open L-subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with

$(g \wedge h)(x) \geq p'$. Thus $\mu = \{f_i\}_{i \in J} \cup \{h'\}$ is a family of γ -open L-subsets with $(\bigvee_{k \in \mu} k(x) \leq p$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$.

In fact, for each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$, if $h(x) \geq p'$, then $(g \wedge h)(x) \geq p'$ which implies that $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i(x) \not\leq p)$, thus $(\bigvee_{k \in \mu} k(x) \not\leq p)$. If $h(x) \not\geq p'$, then $h'(x) \leq p$ which implies $(\bigvee_{k \in \mu} k(x) \leq p)$. From the γ -compactness of g there is a finite subfamily ν of μ say $\nu = \{f_1, \dots, f_n, h'\}$ with $(\bigvee_{k \in \mu} k(x) \leq p)$ for all $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$.

Then $(\bigvee_{i=1}^n f_i(x) \leq p)$ for all $x \in X$ with $(g \wedge h)(x) \geq p'$. Hence $g \wedge h$ is γ -compact.

Corollary 3.14: Let (X, τ) be an γ -compact space and g be a γ -closed, L -subset. Then g is γ -compact.

Theorem 3.15: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space where X is a finite set. Then (X, τ) is γ -compact.

Proof: Let $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a p -level γ -open cover of (X, τ) , where $p \in \text{pr}(L)$. Then $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for all $x \in X$.

Hence, for each $x \in X$ there is $i \in J$ such that $x \in f_i^{-1}(\{t \in T: t \leq p\})$. Since X is finite subset F of J such that $X = \bigcup_{i \in F} f_i^{-1}(\{t \in T: t \leq p\})$, that is, $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for each $x \in X$. Hence (X, τ) is γ -compact.

Corollary 3.16: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space and $g \in L^X$. If g with finite support, then g is γ -compact.

Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. The following δ_ξ will denote the L -topology on X which has the set of all γ -open subsets of (X, τ) as a subbase.

Theorem 3.17: Let (X, δ) be an L -topological space and $g \in L^X$. Then g is γ -compact in (X, τ) if, and only if g is compact in (X, δ_ξ) .

Proof: Let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collection of subbasic δ_ξ -open L -subsets with $(\bigvee_{i \in J} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for all $x \in X$

with $g(x) \geq p'$. Then each f_i is γ -open in (X, τ) and so $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ is a p -level γ -open cover of g . Since g is γ -compact in (X, τ) , there is a finite subset F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$. Hence g is compact in

(X, δ_ξ) . Conversely, let $p \in \text{pr}(L)$ and $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ be a collection of γ -open L -subsets in (X, τ) with $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for

each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$. Since every γ -open L -subsets in (X, τ) is δ_ξ -open by the compactness of g in (X, δ_ξ) , there is a finite subset F of J such that $(\bigvee_{i \in F} f_i(x) \leq p)$ for each $x \in X$ with $g(x) \geq p'$. Hence g is γ -compact in (X, τ) .

Corollary 3.18: An L -topological space (X, τ) is γ -compact if, and only if L -topological space (X, δ_ξ) is compact.

Theorem 3.19: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space. If g is a γ -compact L -subset in (X, τ) then for each closed L -subset h in (X, δ_ξ) , $h \wedge g$ is γ -compact in (X, τ) .

Proof: This follows from Theorem 5.6 and 3.4 in [7].

Definition 3.20: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called:

1. ξ -continuous if, and only if $f: (X, \delta_\xi) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is continuous.
2. ξ' -continuous if, and only if $f: (X, \delta_\xi) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_\xi)$ is continuous.

Corollary 3.21: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a ξ -continuous mapping, then f is ξ -continuous.

Theorem 3.22: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a ξ -continuous mapping with $f^{-1}(y)$ is finite for every $y \in Y$. If $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact in (X, τ) , then $f(g)$ is compact in (Y, σ) .

Proof: This follows from theorem 5.6 and 3.6 in [7].

Corollary 3.23: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a γ -continuous mapping with $f^{-1}(y)$ is finite for every $y \in Y$. If $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact in (X, τ) , then $f(g)$ is compact in (Y, σ) .

Corollary 3.24: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a γ -continuous mapping with $f^{-1}(y)$ is finite for every $y \in Y$. If (X, τ) is γ -compact then (Y, σ) is compact.

Corollary 3.25: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L -topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a ξ -continuous mapping with $f^{-1}(y)$ is finite for every $y \in Y$. If $g \in L^X$ is γ -compact in (X, τ) , then $f(g)$ is γ -compact in (Y, σ) .

Proof: This follows from theorem 5.6 and 3.6 in [7].

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